

AI-Driven personalisation in social media marketing: Opportunities and ethical challenges

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Abstract: The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in social media marketing has enabled new frontiers of personalisation, allowing brands to tailor content, advertising, and user experiences in real time based on behavioural, demographic, and psychographic data. This study synthesizes recent research on the applications, benefits, and ethical challenges of AI-driven personalisation within social media environments. It explores how AI facilitates consumer segmentation, dynamic content delivery, and influencer alignment, while also raising critical concerns related to privacy, algorithmic bias, transparency, manipulation, and user autonomy. The paper employs a thematic analysis to identify key opportunities such as enhanced engagement, operational efficiency, and predictive adaptation. It also examines the complex ethical implications emerging from algorithmic personalisation practices. The study concludes with a proposed research agenda and practical recommendations focused on ethical design, regulatory innovation, and user empowerment in the evolving landscape of AI-enabled marketing.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, personalisation, social media marketing, ethical challenges, algorithmic bias, consumer privacy*

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and rationale

The last decade has witnessed a seismic shift in how brands engage with consumers—moving from massmarket communication to hyperpersonalised interaction. This transformation has been catalysed by the integration of AI technologies into social media marketing (e.g., machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing) (Chintalapati & Pandey, 2021; Kumar et al., 2024). AI allows marketers to process large volumes of behavioural, demographic, and contextual data in real time, enabling dynamic segmentation, tailored recommendations, and influencer matching (Rahima, 2025; Khamoushi, 2024). Empirical studies highlight the growing impact of AI-driven personalisation on consumer behaviour (Beyari & Hashem, 2025). However, AI-driven personalisation also raises ethical concerns related to privacy, bias, manipulation, and trust (Saura et al., 2024; Meng & Liu, 2025). The deployment of AI in social media marketing thus represents a dual-edge scenario: brands gain precision and scale, while consumers and society face risks.

1.2. Aim and scope

This study aims to synthesise scholarly literature from 2017 onward on how AI enables personalisation in social media marketing and to critically examine the ethical implications of these practices. The scope includes: personalisation enabled by AI (recommendation engines, segmentation, dynamic content adaptation) within a social media marketing context; outcomes for both brands (engagement, ROI, efficiency) and consumers (experience, loyalty, trust); ethical and regulatory concerns (privacy, bias, manipulation, transparency). The study is restricted to social media marketing contexts, although findings may have relevance for other digital channels.

The study addresses the following research questions:

RQ1. How has AI been applied to achieve personalisation in social media marketing?

RQ2. What are the documented benefits of AI-driven personalisation for brands and consumers in social media contexts?

RQ3. What ethical challenges have emerged in the literature related to AI-driven personalisation (e.g., privacy, manipulation, bias, transparency)?

2. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Defining AI and personalisation in social media marketing

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in marketing refers to algorithmic tools such as predictive analytics, recommendation systems, automated content generation, sentiment analysis, and real-time decision making (Chintalapati & Pandey, 2021; Chandra et al., 2022; Kumar et al., 2024). Personalisation is defined as tailoring messages, content, offers, or experiences to individual users based on data about their behaviour, preferences, or context (Lim & Rasul, 2022; Rolando, 2024; Kudapa, 2024).

In social media marketing, personalisation is shaped by the platforms' social, interactive, and data-rich nature. Social media platforms resolve huge volumes of user interactions (likes, comments, shares, follows) and enable dynamic adjustments of content in real time (Khamoushi, 2024; Rahima, 2025; Beyari & Hashem, 2025). The typology of personalisation in social media can include: segmentation vs individualisation; static vs dynamic; content adaptation vs influencer matching vs advertisement targeting.

2.2. Theoretical frameworks

Several theoretical perspectives provide a foundation for understanding how AI-driven personalisation operates in social media marketing and how users respond to such practices. These frameworks explain both user engagement mechanisms and the broader ethical and power implications associated with algorithmic decision-making. Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) offers an important lens for analysing personalised content consumption in social media environments. Originally developed to explain why individuals actively select particular media to satisfy specific psychological and social needs, UGT empha-

sises user agency rather than passive media exposure (Katz et al., 1974). According to this perspective, users engage with media content to fulfil cognitive needs (information seeking), affective needs (emotional gratification), personal integrative needs (self-esteem and identity), and social integrative needs (interaction and belonging).

In the context of AI-driven social media marketing, UGT helps explain why personalised content often generates higher engagement levels. Algorithmic systems analyse user behaviour, preferences, and contextual data to deliver content that aligns closely with individual motivations and interests. When personalisation successfully addresses users' perceived needs—such as relevance, entertainment, or social validation—it increases the likelihood of attention, interaction, and sustained platform use. However, while UGT highlights the benefits of relevance and gratification, it also raises questions about the extent to which user choice remains autonomous when preferences are continuously shaped by predictive algorithms.

Privacy Calculus Theory provides a complementary perspective by focusing on how users evaluate the risks and benefits associated with personalised marketing practices. This theory posits that individuals make rational—or boundedly rational—decisions about information disclosure by weighing perceived benefits, such as convenience and relevance, against perceived risks, including privacy loss and data misuse (Culnan & Bies, 2003). In digital environments, this cost-benefit assessment is ongoing and context-dependent.

Within AI-driven social media marketing, Privacy Calculus Theory explains why users may tolerate extensive data collection in exchange for personalised experiences. Algorithmic personalisation can offer tangible value, such as tailored recommendations or reduced information overload, which may offset privacy concerns in users' evaluations. However, as data practices become increasingly opaque and algorithmic inferences grow more intrusive, the perceived balance may shift. Recent research suggests that asymmetries in information and power between platforms and users complicate the calculus, potentially undermining informed consent and amplifying ethical concerns (Meng & Liu, 2025).

A third relevant perspective is Algorithmic Gatekeeping, informed by the Two-Step Flow theory adapted to the digital and algorithmic era. Traditional two-step flow models emphasised the role of human opinion leaders in mediating information exposure. In contemporary social media ecosystems, this me-

diating role has increasingly been assumed by algorithms that filter, prioritise, and personalise content at scale (Soffer, 2021). These systems shape what users see, when they see it, and how often, thereby influencing attention, attitudes, and behaviour.

In social media marketing, algorithmic gatekeeping has significant implications for power, autonomy, and influence. AI-driven personalisation does not merely respond to user preferences but actively structures information environments, reinforcing certain narratives while marginalising others. This shift raises normative questions regarding transparency, accountability, and the concentration of communicative power in platform-controlled systems. Understanding personalisation through the lens of algorithmic gatekeeping highlights the need to critically examine not only engagement outcomes but also the broader societal consequences of AI-mediated marketing practices.

3. METHODOLOGY

This article adopts a narrative integrative literature review methodology synthesising scholarly work published between 2017 and 2025 on the topic of AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing. The study is structured to identify core themes, opportunities, and ethical tensions by collating and critically evaluating peer-reviewed studies, conference proceedings, and selected grey literature (industry reports, white papers) (Snyder, 2019).

3.1. Research design

The study followed a three-phase approach inspired by principles of systematic literature review (SLR) and thematic analysis:

1. Literature Identification;
2. Inclusion/Exclusion Filtering;
3. Thematic Synthesis.

This method was selected to balance depth and breadth, enabling both comprehensive coverage and detailed qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Boell & CecezKecmanovic, 2015).

3.2. Literature search strategy

A systematic search was conducted using the following academic databases and platforms: Scopus, Web of Science, EBSCOhost (Business Source Complete), ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar,

and PMC (for interdisciplinary AI ethics publications). Industry insights were drawn from sources such as Stein et al. (2025) to contextualise practitioner perspectives.

Search queries combined terms such as: („artificial intelligence“ OR „AI“) AND („personalisation“ OR „recommendation“) AND („social media marketing“ OR „SMM“) AND („ethics“ OR „privacy“ OR „bias“ OR „manipulation“)

The search was constrained to English-language publications from January 2017 to September 2025 to reflect recent developments in AI and social media marketing.

3.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

A total of 128 articles and documents were initially identified. After screening titles and abstracts, 68 sources were selected for full-text review. Of these, 35 core publications were retained for inclusion in the final synthesis, based on direct relevance, empirical or conceptual contribution, and scholarly rigour. Inclusion criteria included: peer-reviewed journal articles or high-quality industry reports; explicit focus on AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing; publication from 2017 onward; and discussion of outcomes and/or ethical implications. Exclusion criteria included: publications before 2017; articles focusing solely on general AI applications outside social media marketing; purely technical AI papers without marketing context; and non-English publications.

3.4. Thematic analysis and synthesis

A qualitative thematic analysis approach was employed, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework: familiarisation with data; generating initial codes; searching for themes; reviewing themes; defining and naming themes; and producing the report. Themes were organised under three analytical categories: Opportunities of AI personalisation, Ethical challenges, and Implications & research gaps. Each selected article was coded accordingly and synthesised to identify patterns, contradictions, and gaps.

4. OPPORTUNITIES OF AI-DRIVEN PERSONALISATION IN SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing offers several interrelated benefits for both brands and consumers. Below, we break these down in more detail.

4.1. Enhanced consumer engagement and experience

One of the primary advantages of AI personalisation is its ability to elevate the relevance and timeliness of content delivered to users. For instance, AI systems can analyse vast quantities of behavioural data (clicks, likes, shares, dwell time) and social context (friends, groups, influencer networks) to craft messages that resonate with an individual's preferences and state of mind. A recent empirical study found that the use of AI in social media marketing within the MENA region was significantly related to improved consumer purchase intention and platform choice, demonstrating that personalisation mediated via AI boosts engagement and conversion (Teepapal, 2025; Beyari & Hashem, 2025).

Moreover, platforms and marketers are now enabling “nextbest” interactions or content suggestions in real time, rather than relying solely on static segmentation. For example, a McKinsey report notes that generative AI and integrated platforms are unlocking the “next frontier” of personalized marketing by orchestrating seamless interactions across touchpoints (Stein et al., 2025; Møller et al., 2025).

From the consumer side, personalised content also enhances the user experience: when content appears more aligned to one's interests, learning style, or context (for example, time of day or location), it feels less “advertising” and more “value add”. This tends to deepen brand loyalty and increase userplatform engagement. However, while empirical studies consistently report positive effects on engagement, most rely on short-term behavioural metrics, offering limited insight into long-term user satisfaction or potential engagement fatigue.

4.2. Efficiency and effectiveness for brands

For brands and marketers, AI-driven personalisation delivers operational efficiencies and greater effectiveness. Traditional marketing required relatively broad segmentation and manual campaign adjustments; AI now enables microsegmentation, real-time A/B testing, automated creative adaptations, and dynamic budget allocation (Kumar et al., 2024; Sherly Steffi et al., 2025). In social media marketing contexts, these capabilities are especially powerful: influencer matching via AI algorithms, automated postoptimisation based on user reaction data, and adaptive content delivery (Beyari & Hashem, 2025) all reduce manual effort and enhance ROI.

Additionally, AI enables a kind of “always-on” marketing: systems monitor engagement metrics continuously and adapt content, timing, format, or channels accordingly. This responsiveness means brands can react faster to shifting consumer behaviour or social trends, giving them a competitive edge (An & Ngo, 2025). Although the literature broadly agrees on efficiency gains, relatively few studies examine the organisational risks or dependency effects associated with automated, always-on personalisation systems.

4.3. Predictive analytics and real-time adaptation

Beyond enhancing what is currently delivered, AI enables forecasting of future behaviour — enabling marketers to preempt user needs rather than only respond. Machine learning models can predict likely churn, intention to purchase, or content preference shifts, enabling timely interventions or personalised offers (Tirtayani et al., 2024). Real-time adaptation means that when a user's behaviour changes (e.g., interest in a new topic, shift in social network), the system can dynamically adjust what the brand presents. This continuous datainsightaction cycle means personalisation becomes increasingly effective over time. As a recent study notes, personalized stimuli driven by AI on social media can significantly influence user engagement metrics (Teepapal, 2025).

In sum, the opportunities exist not only for better user experiences and greater efficiency, but for more anticipatory, data-driven marketing that evolves with consumer behaviour. Nevertheless, the predominantly optimistic framing of predictive personalisation contrasts with a smaller but growing body of work warning that predictive accuracy does not necessarily translate into perceived user value or trust.

5. ETHICAL CHALLENGES AND RISKS

While the opportunities are substantial, the literature increasingly emphasises that AI-driven personalisation also brings serious ethical and societal risks. Below are key themes.

5.1. Privacy, data collection, and transparency

Personalisation requires large volumes of data about user behaviour, context, and often social networks. This raises major consent, awareness, and control is-

sues. For example, users may not fully understand the extent to which their social media interactions, inferred preferences, or even location data are used to shape the content they receive. A systematic literature review of AI personalisation ethics emphasises risks of surveillance, loss of autonomy, and data misuse (Saura et al., 2024; Teraiya & Krishnamurthy, 2025).

Transparency is another concern: “blackbox” algorithms and dynamic personalisation make it difficult for users to know *why* certain content or ads are being shown. Without clear user-facing explanations, trust can erode. Regulatory frameworks such as the GDPR aim to require transparency and user rights, yet many AI personalisation applications remain opaque (Teepapal, 2025). While most studies frame extensive data collection as a threat to user autonomy, some research suggests that users may tolerate such practices when perceived benefits are clear, highlighting an unresolved tension in the literature.

5.2. Algorithmic bias and discrimination

Even when data is collected “fairly”, AI models can reproduce or amplify societal biases. In marketing personalisation contexts, this may manifest as certain demographic segments being over-targeted (or under-targeted), stereotype reinforcement, or exclusion of minority voices. Research on large language models used for marketing slogans found that certain demographic groups (e.g., women, low-income earners) received markedly different or less empowering messages compared to others (Ali et al., 2019; Grewal et al., 2025).

Similarly, AI models trained on historic data that reflects bias may produce skewed outcomes in content delivery or influencer matching. The result is not just uneven performance but potential discrimination or reputational harm for brands (Kumar et al., 2024). Thus, bias mitigation and fairness auditing become central ethical obligations. Bias audits and fairness frameworks remain underdeveloped (Hari et al., 2025; Bell et al., 2024). However, findings on algorithmic bias vary across platforms and data contexts, suggesting that bias is not an inevitable outcome of personalisation but is strongly shaped by design choices and training data.

5.3. Manipulation, autonomy, and filter bubbles

Personalised content, when extremely tailored, poses a risk of manipulation. The line between helpful rel-

evance and persuasive exploitation is thin. Hyper-personalisation may lead users into “filter bubbles”, where they only see content that reinforces their beliefs, preferences, or behaviour, reducing exposure to diverse perspectives (Sirbu et al., 2019; Soffer, 2021). In marketing contexts, this means consumers may be steered subtly toward certain decisions (purchases, opinions) without full awareness.

The notion of algorithmic gatekeeping describes how algorithms increasingly replace human opinionleaders and editorial oversight, placing power into opaque systems (Soffer, 2021). From an ethical point of view, users’ autonomy—ability to make informed, independent decisions—is thus at risk. A recent Forbes article warns that AI in marketing may become a “slippery slope” toward behaviour manipulation (Clark, 2024). Generative AI-based influencers and targeted messaging may cross the line from persuasion into manipulation (Møller et al., 2025). Although many scholars warn of manipulation and filter bubbles, empirical evidence of direct behavioural harm remains fragmented, indicating a need for more causal and longitudinal research.

5.4. Accountability and governance

As AI models become more complex, the question of accountability becomes urgent: Who is responsible if a personalised marketing campaign causes harm—consumer distress, discrimination, privacy breach? Brands, platforms, algorithm developers? Without clear governance and transparency, it is difficult to assign responsibility. The lack of explainability in many AI systems further complicates this (Hardiansyah & Judijanto, 2025). Ethical design and algorithmic audits are still emerging fields in marketing contexts (Clark, 2024). Also, current laws (e.g., GDPR) don’t fully address this complexity (Teepapal, 2025). Despite growing calls for governance and audit mechanisms, the literature offers limited empirical evaluation of their real-world effectiveness, leaving a gap between normative proposals and operational practice.

6. IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE AND REGULATION

The findings of this review indicate that AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing generates important implications across three interconnected domains: marketing practice, platform and system design, and public policy and regulation. Address-

ing the opportunities and risks of personalisation requires coordinated action by practitioners who deploy AI tools, platforms that govern algorithmic infrastructures, and regulators responsible for safeguarding consumer rights and societal values. Rather than operating independently, these factors shape a shared ecosystem in which ethical, transparent, and accountable personalisation must be jointly sustained.

From a marketing practice perspective, organisations must embed ethics-by-design principles into the development and execution of personalised social media strategies. This involves moving beyond performance-driven optimisation toward responsible data practices, including transparent communication about how personal data are collected and used, meaningful user control over personalisation settings, and strict data-minimisation policies (AnalytixLabs, 2024; Hasan et al., 2025). Regular audits for algorithmic bias and discrimination are also essential, particularly as AI systems increasingly rely on inferred attributes and behavioural predictions rather than explicitly provided data. At the same time, brands must balance short-term performance gains with long-term trust and legitimacy. Highly intrusive personalisation may generate short-term gains but increase reputational risks (Saura et al., 2024). Sustainable practice, therefore, requires transparent consent mechanisms, clearly visible explanations such as “why am I seeing this?” indicators, diversity-aware targeting and influencer-matching processes, and ongoing human oversight of automated marketing decisions. These measures help preserve user autonomy while maintaining the effectiveness of AI-driven personalisation.

Social media platforms and technology developers play a central role in shaping the personalisation ecosystem, as they function as algorithmic gatekeepers that mediate content visibility and commercial influence. Platforms bear responsibility for establishing robust governance frameworks that ensure transparency, fairness, and accountability in personalisation systems. This includes publishing algorithmic transparency reports, offering explainability interfaces that clarify recommendation logic, and providing user-friendly dashboards that allow individuals to adjust or opt out of personalisation features (Clark, 2024). In addition, platforms must enforce ethical standards for third-party marketers and tool developers operating within their ecosystems.

Effective platform governance also requires systematic data and model oversight. Personalisation algorithms should be subject to regular audits to ensure representativeness, bias mitigation, data security, and

appropriate anonymisation practices (AnalytixLabs, 2024). Allowing users to modify the intensity or scope of personalisation further strengthens agency and trust, while reinforcing platforms’ accountability for the social consequences of algorithmic curation.

Finally, the study highlights significant implications for policymakers and regulators. Existing data protection frameworks, such as GDPR and CCPA, primarily address issues of data collection and consent, but are less equipped to govern real-time, adaptive AI personalisation. As personalisation systems increasingly shape consumer choice and exposure, regulatory attention must expand to include algorithmic transparency, explainability, fairness, and auditability (Saura et al., 2024). The introduction of mandatory algorithmic impact assessments for high-risk personalisation systems has been proposed as a mechanism to identify and mitigate potential harms before large-scale deployment.

Regulators must also clarify questions of liability and responsibility when AI-driven personalisation leads to adverse outcomes, such as discriminatory exclusion or behavioural manipulation. The development of shared ethical metrics—covering fairness, transparency, autonomy, and trust—would support more consistent regulatory enforcement. Given the global operation of social media platforms, cross-jurisdictional coordination is essential to prevent regulatory fragmentation and ensure effective oversight across national boundaries (Teepapal, 2025; Hari et al., 2025; Teraiya & Krishnamurthy, 2025).

7. RESEARCH GAPS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Despite the growing body of literature on AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing, several limitations and research gaps remain evident. Much of the existing scholarship is conceptual or technically oriented, with relatively few empirical studies examining how users perceive, experience, and respond to personalised marketing practices. In particular, limited attention has been paid to how consumers evaluate the trade-offs between relevance and privacy, or to the psychological and behavioural consequences of sustained algorithmic targeting (Rolando, 2024; Meng & Liu, 2025). Moreover, the long-term effects of hyperpersonalisation on trust, brand relationships, and user fatigue remain underexplored, as most studies rely on cross-sectional designs rather than longitudinal approaches (Obiegbu & Larsen, 2024).

Table 1: Synthesis of research themes on AI-Driven personalisation in social media marketing

Section	Theme / Subtopic	Description	Citations
Opportunities of AI-Driven personalisation	Enhanced engagement and experience	AI creates relevant, emotionally resonant content, improving click-through and loyalty.	Beyari & Hashem (2025); Kumar et al. (2024)
	Efficiency and effectiveness for brands	Automation of targeting, content adaptation, and budget allocation improves ROI.	Chintalapati & Pandey (2021); An & Ngo, (2025)
	Predictive analytics and real-time adaptation	AI forecasts user behaviour, enabling adaptive marketing in real time.	Tirtayani et al. (2024); Teepapal (2025)
Ethical challenges and risks	Privacy and transparency	Extensive data collection and opaque algorithms raise concerns about user consent and data control.	Saura et al. (2024); Aïmeur et al. (2019)
	Algorithmic bias and discrimination	Biased training data or targeting can lead to exclusion or reinforcement of stereotypes.	Grewal et al.(2025); Ali et al. (2019)
	Manipulation and autonomy	Hyper-personalisation may exploit psychological vulnerabilities and reduce exposure to diverse content.	Sirbu et al. (2019); Soffer (2021)
	Transparency and accountability	Black-box AI limits understanding and makes it difficult to assign responsibility.	Hardiansyah & Judijanto (2025); Clark (2024)
Implications for practice and regulation	Marketing practice	Brands should follow ethical-by-design, minimise data use, and ensure explainability.	AnalytixLabs (2024); Saura et al. (2024)
	Platform governance	Platforms must offer user control, publish algorithmic audits, and regulate 3rd-party APIs.	Clark (2024); Stein et al. (2025)
	Policy and regulation	Laws must evolve to include algorithmic fairness, transparency, and redress mechanisms.	Saura et al. (2024); Teepapal (2025)

Source: Authors

Future research would benefit from greater methodological and contextual diversity. Longitudinal studies are needed to assess how attitudes toward personalisation evolve, while cross-platform and cross-cultural comparisons could illuminate how personalisation practices and ethical perceptions differ across social media environments and regulatory contexts (Obiegbu & Larsen, 2024; Beyari & Hashem, 2025). In addition, there is currently no widely accepted framework for evaluating ethical outcomes such as fairness, transparency, autonomy, and trust in AI-driven personalisation. Advancing the field requires the development and empirical testing of standardised ethical metrics that can be applied consistently across platforms and marketing contexts (Saura et al., 2024; Hasan et al., 2025).

This study is also subject to several limitations that shape these future research directions. The analysis was restricted to English-language publications and

publicly accessible academic and industry sources, potentially excluding relevant research from non-English-speaking regions and proprietary industry studies. While a systematic review protocol was applied, selection and interpretation biases cannot be fully eliminated, and the rapid evolution of AI technologies means that some emerging practices may not yet be reflected in the literature. Addressing these limitations will require interdisciplinary, mixed-method research that integrates insights from marketing, data science, ethics, and law—particularly as generative AI introduces new forms of dynamic, content-creating personalisation with distinct ethical and societal implications (Kumar et al., 2024; Møller et al., 2025).

8. CONCLUSION

AI-driven personalisation has fundamentally transformed social media marketing, enabling brands to en-

hance user engagement, optimise campaign efficiency, and anticipate consumer behaviour with unprecedented precision (Chintalapati & Pandey, 2021; Kumar et al., 2024). Through advanced data analytics and algorithmic decision-making, platforms are now capable of delivering highly tailored experiences at scale.

However, the findings of this study also reveal substantial ethical and societal challenges associated with these developments. AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing raises persistent concerns regarding privacy intrusion, algorithmic bias, behavioural manipulation, and a lack of transparency and accountability (Saura et al., 2024; Grewal et al., 2025). As personalisation expands, ethical boundaries become increasingly contested. From a practical perspective, sustainable implementation of AI-driven personalisation requires the adoption of ethics-by-design principles, robust algorithmic governance, and greater transparency in data use and automated decision-making. Platforms must assume a proactive role in ensuring fairness and accountability, while regulators need to strengthen and adapt policy frameworks to reflect the evolving capabilities of AI-based marketing systems.

Importantly, this study identifies several gaps in the existing literature that point to clear directions for future research. Empirical studies examining consumer perceptions of AI-driven personalisation across different cultural, regulatory, and platform contexts remain limited. Moreover, there is a lack of longitudinal research assessing the long-term psychological, behavioural, and societal impacts of algorithmic personalisation. Future research should also explore interdisciplinary approaches that integrate marketing, ethics, law, and computer science, with particular attention to transparency mechanisms, explainable AI, and bias mitigation strategies.

In conclusion, while AI-driven personalisation in social media marketing offers significant opportunities for enhanced engagement and operational efficiency, these benefits are inseparable from substantial ethical risks. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated action from researchers, practitioners, platforms, and policymakers. Only by advancing research that balances innovation with responsibility can AI-driven personalisation deliver value that is not only effective but also fair, inclusive, and trustworthy.

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Apstrakt

Personalizacija vođena veštačkom inteligencijom u marketingu na društvenim mrežama: prilike i etički izazovi

Konstantinos Papageorgiou, Konstantinos Milioris

Integracija veštačke inteligencije (AI) u marketingu na društvenim mrežama omogućila je nove granice personalizacije, dozvoljavajući brendovima da prilagode sadržaj, oglašavanje i korisnička iskustva u realnom vremenu na osnovu bihevioralnih, demografskih i psihografskih podataka. Ova studija sintetizuje prethodna istraživanja o primenama, prednostima i etičkim izazovima personalizacije vođene veštačkom inteligencijom u okruženjima društvenih mreža. Studija istražuje kako AI omogućava segmentaciju potrošača, dinamičku isporuku sadržaja i usklađivanje influensera, dok istovremeno pokreće kritične zabrinutosti vezane za privatnost, algoritamsku pristrasnost, transparentnost, manipulaciju i autonomiju korisnika. Rad kori-

sti tematsku analizu kako bi identifikovao ključne prilike kao što su povećano angažovanje, operativna efikasnost i prediktivna adaptacija. Takođe ispituje složene etičke implikacije koje proističu iz praksi algoritamske personalizacije. Rad se završava predloženom istraživačkom agendom i praktičnim preporukama usmerenim na etički dizajn, regulatorne inovacije i osnaživanje korisnika u evolutivnom pejzažu marketinga omogućenom veštačkom inteligencijom.

Ključne reči: *veštačka inteligencija, personalizacija, marketing na društvenim mrežama, etički izazovi, algoritamska pristrasnost, privatnost potrošača*

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